

13th INTERNATIONAL
CONGRESS
OF THE SERBIAN SOCIETY
OF TOXICOLOGY

1st TOXSEE
REGIONAL
CONFERENCE

Present and Future of toxicology: Challenges and opportunities

10 - 12 May, 2023 Belgrade

electronic

ABSTRACT
BOOK

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DEAR COLLEAGUES, DEAR FRIENDS,

We are delighted to greet you on the **13th International Congress of the Serbian Society of Toxicology & 1. TOXSEE Regional Conference - Present and Future of toxicology: challenges and opportunities**, organized in Belgrade from 10-12 May 2023.

Five years after our last international Congress we gathered in Belgrade, to further promote contemporary toxicology, in the broadest sense of meaning, as a response to the new challenges requiring innovative approaches and solutions, as it is understood in the third decade of the XXI century.

Initial concept, to blend the top scientific level in toxicology with the potentials of its' use in broad array of clinical and other domains, proved to be right. Line-up of more than 70 first class international and regional faculties as well as best Serbian scientists and toxicology professionals in all related domains fully justify the approach. Moreover, interest and presence of more than 250 colleagues from Serbia and region witness that our professional community has recognized the approach taken and shown vast interest.

The Serbian Society of Toxicology is committed to innovation and creativity in research and education, in cooperation with collegial associations and institutions in Serbia and abroad. As a regional leader, we developed and inaugurated the regional brand TOXSEE, with the idea to gather as much as possible expertise and know-how from the region and Europe, to capture knowledge, share experience and exchange practical skills with colleagues who deal with toxicology problems daily.

Time imposes on us the need to integrate science, top knowledge and daily practice in a quality and efficient way, to contribute to the better health of the society as a whole in the most purposeful manner. Therefore, a thematic and functional connections with domains of emergency medicine, general medicine, paediatrics, ecology, in addition to already standard toxicological disciplines i.e. clinical, forensic, occupational, and experimental toxicology have been enhanced.

We are glad to host you in a pleasant atmosphere of Belgrade in mid-May, to benefit from the attractive and dynamic program, exchange knowledge, and, equally important, to refresh existing and establish new contacts with colleagues and friends, while enjoying our hospitality and cherish the moment in one of the best partying cities of Europe.

YOU ARE MOST WELCOME!!!

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- President of the 13th STC Congress

Petar Bulat

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MOŽE LI BISFENOL A DOPRINETI GOJAZNOSTI KOD PCOS?

ENDOCRINE
DISRUPTORS

**Maja Milanović¹, Nataša Milošević¹, Jan Sudji¹, Stefan Stojanoski^{2,3}, Milica Atanacković
Krstonošić¹, Bojan Vuković^{2,4}, Artur Bjelica^{5,6}, Nataša Milić¹, Milica Medić Stojanoska^{2,4}**

1 Univerzitet u Novom Sadu – Medicinski fakultet, Katedra za farmaciju, Novi Sad, **Srbija**

2 Univerzitet u Novom Sadu – Medicinski fakultet, Novi Sad, **Srbija**

3 Institut za onkologiju Vojvodine, Sremska Kamenica, **Srbija**

4 Klinika za endokrinologiju, dijabetes i bolesti metabolizma, Klinički centar Vojvodine,
Novi Sad, **Srbija**

5 Univerzitet u Novom Sadu – Medicinski fakultet, Katedra za ginekologiju i akušerstvo,
Novi Sad, **Srbija**

6 Klinika za ginekologiju i akušerstvo, Klinički centar Vojvodine, Novi Sad, **Srbija**

Danas sve veću pažnju privlače efekti bisfenola A (BPA) na ženski reproduktivni sistem. Cilj istraživanja bio je da se ispita prisustvo BPA kod žena sa sindromom policističnih jajnika (PCOS) i potencijalni uticaj BPA na povećanje telesne mase. Sprovedena studija preseka uključivala je 29 žena u reproduktivnom periodu sa dijagnostifikovanim PCOS. Prisustvo bilo koje druge endokrine ili autoimune bolesti je isključeno. Nivoi BPA su određeni u jutarnjem urinu gasnom hromatografijom sa masenom spektrometrijom.

BPA je detektovan u polovini ispitivanog uzorka u koncentraciji do 39 ng/μg Cr. PCOS BPA+ žene su imale povećan indeks telesne mase (BMI) i obim struka (WC) u odnosu na PCOS BPA- žene (28,65 prema 20,1 kg/m² i 90,5 prema 72 cm, respektivno). Polovina žena sa BMI preko 30 imala je BPA u urinu. Pored toga, PCOS BPA+ žene su imale skoro 7 puta veći rizik za WC iznad 80 cm (granična vrednost za prekomernu telesnu masu) i 4 puta veću verovatnoću da će imati BMI veći od 30 (granična vrednost za gojaznost). Statistički značajno veće vrednosti količnika obima struka i visine (WtHR) su zabeležene kod PCOS BPA+ žena u poređenju sa PCOS BPA- (0,55 u odnosu na 0,42, p=0,046). Takođe, PCOS BPA+ žene imale su veći rizik za WtHR iznad 0,5. Iako je gojaznost uobičajena kod PCOS, dobijeni rezultati sugerišu da su žene izložene BPA u većem riziku da imaju prekomernu telesnu masu ili visceralnu gojaznost. Neophodna su dalja istraživanja kako bi se bolje istražili efekti BPA kod PCOS žena.

KLJUČNE REČI: bisfenol A, PCOS, endokrini disruptori, urin, gojaznost

MAY BISPEHOL A INDUCE OBESITY IN PCOS?

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Maja Milanović¹, Nataša Milošević¹, Jan Sudji¹, Stefan Stojanoski^{2,3}, Milica Atanacković
Krstonošić¹, Bojan Vuković^{2,4}, Artur Bjelica^{5,6}, Nataša Milić¹, Milica Medić Stojanoska^{2,4}

1 *University of Novi Sad – Faculty of medicine, Department of pharmacy, Novi Sad, Serbia*

2 *University of Novi Sad – Faculty of medicine, Novi Sad, Serbia*

3 *Oncology institute of Vojvodina, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia*

4 *Clinic for endocrinology, diabetes and metabolic diseases, Clinical center of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia*

5 *University of Novi Sad – Faculty of medicine, Department of gynecology and obstetrics, Novi Sad, Serbia*

6 *Clinics for gynecology and obstetrics, Clinical center of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia*

Nowadays, bisphenol A (BPA) effects on female reproductive system attract growing attention. The aim of the research was to investigate the BPA occurrence in women with polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) and its possible influence on the increase of body weight. This cross-sectional study was performed on 29 PCOS women in reproductive period without any other endocrine or autoimmune disease. BPA levels were determined in morning spot urine by gas-chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry.

BPA was detected in almost half of the examined sample in concentration up to 39 ng/μg Cr. PCOS BPA+ women had increased body mass index (BMI) and waist circumference (WC) in comparison to non-exposed ones (28.65 versus 20.1 kg/m² and 90.5 versus 72 cm, respectively). Half of PCOS women with BMI over 30 had BPA in their urine. Additionally, PCOS BPA+ women had almost 7 times higher risk for WC above 80 cm (cut-off for overweight) and 4 times are more likely to have BMI higher than 30 (cut-off for obesity). Considering the waist-to high-ratio (WtHR), the statistically significant higher values were observed in PCOS BPA+ women in comparison to PCOS BPA- (0.55 versus 0.42, p=0.046). Also, PCOS BPA+ women are at higher risk to have WtHR more than 0.5. Although obesity is generally common among PCOS women, the obtained results suggest that BPA exposed women are at higher risk to be overweight, obese or with visceral obesity. Further research is needed in order to better explore the BPA effects on exacerbating and potentiating some PCOS features.

KEYWORDS: bisphenol A, PCOS, endocrine disruptors, urine, obesity